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MICROWAVE ASSISTED SYNTHESIS OF 1, 8-DIOXOCTAHYDROXANTHENES USING PHOSPHONITRILIC CHLORIDE AS CATALYST

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ABSTRACT

Microwave assisted effective procedure for the synthesis of 1,8-dioxooctahydroxanthenes through one-pot condensation of aldehydes and dimedone using Phosphonitrilic Chloride as catalyst and tetra butyl ammonium bromide as phase transfer catalyst was described. Aromatic aldehydes having electron withdrawing or electron donating groups reacted with dimedone to give corresponding 1,8-dioxooctahydroxanthenes derivatives in moderate to good yields.

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INTRODUCTION

The use of microwave irradiation in organic synthesis has become increasingly popular within the pharmaceutical and academic areas, because it is a new enabling technology for drug discovery and development [1-13]. New synthetic applications show a variety of new chemistries performed with microwave irradiation. Leadbeater and co-workers [14] have shown that reacting an activated aryl bromide with an arylboronic acid in water, using tetra-butyl ammonium bromide (TBAB) as a phase-transfer catalyst (PTC), results in a successfully coupled biaryl Suzuki product without the aid of a palladium catalyst. In addition, a transition-metal-free Sonogashira reaction between an aryl bromide or iodide and phenylacetylene results in respectable yields [15]. In this case, polyethylene glycol was used as the phase-transfer agent. One interesting example is the palladium-catalyzed amination of (azahetero) aryl chlorides. Aryl chlorides are known to be quite unreactive due to the C–Cl bond strength, but with microwave heating for 10 minutes, these aminations were reactive [16]. Microwave-assisted, improved intramolecular amination of aryl bromides to benzimidazoles [17] is another example.

Microwave irradiation is fast becoming a source of energy for biochemical applications. Many of the biochemical molecules are temperature-sensitive. At present, there have been studies published on carbohydrates [18-24], nucleosides [25-30], peptides [31-39], proteins [14, 40,41], peptoids [42] the polymerase chain reaction (PCR), and trypsin digestion. Keeping in view the applications of microwave chemistry, we herein report our studies of microwave assisted synthesis of 1,8-dioxooctahydroxanthenes using PNT as catalyst and TBAB as PTC.

Xanthene derivatives has attracted the considerable interest of the chemists because of their wide range of biological and pharmaceutical properties like antiviral, [43-44] antibacterial [45], anti-inflammatory [46-47], anticancer [48], anti-nociceptive [49] and anti-plasmodial [50] etc activities. These are also used as sensitizers in photodynamic therapy [51, 52], as antagonists of paralyzing action of zoxazolamine [53], leuco-dyes [54], laser technology [55], as versatile synthons because of the inherent reactivity of the inbuilt pyran ring [56]. 1,8-dioxooctahydroxanthenes are very important derivative of xanthenes in which a phenyl substituted pyran ring is fused on either side with two cyclohexenone rings. 1,8-dioxooctahydroxanthenes have wide range of applications in the field of medicinal chemistry. It shows biological activities such as antiviral, antibacterial and anti-inflammatory activities [57]. Several methods were developed and adopted to synthesize 1,8-dioxooctahydroxanthenes including cyclo dehydration, trapping of benzynes by phenol [58], the cyclocondensation of 2-hydroxy aromatic aldehydes and 2-tetralone [59-60]. These procedures involve acid or base-catalysed condensation of active methylene carbonyl compounds with aldehydes. However, these methods have limitations of prolonged reaction times, poor yields and side reactions of aldehydes.

Synthetic methods reported using variety of catalysts/reagents such as Silica sulphuric acid [61], Dowex-50 W [62], $\text{HClO}_4 \cdot \text{SiO}_2$ and $\text{PPA} \cdot \text{SiO}_2$ [63], Fe^{3+} -Montmorillonite [64], Diammonium hydrogen phosphate [65], TMSCl [66], Tetrabutyl ammonium hydrogen sulphate [67], Hydrochloric acid [68], $\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot \text{SiO}_2$ [69], Cyanuric chloride [70], BiCl_3 [71], SelectfluorTM [72], $\text{NaHSO}_4 \cdot \text{SiO}_2$ and Silica chloride [73], $\text{InCl}_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in ionic liquid [74], *p*-Dodecylbenzenesulfonic acid (DBSA) [59, 60], *p*-TSA [75], Amberlyst-15 [76], ZnO-nano particle, [77] Fe- Cu/ZSM-5 [78] Ce-ZSM-11 Zeolite [79], FeNP@SBA-15 [80].

Present work

In the present work, we herein report the microwave assisted synthesis of 1,8-dioxooctahydroxanthene derivatives III by the condensation of a variety of aldehydes I, with dimedone II in water using phosphonitrilic chloride as catalyst and TBAB as PTC (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1.

Experimental procedure

A mixture of aromatic aldehyde (1 mmol), dimedone (2 mmol), and phosphonitrilic chloride (0.1 mmol) as catalyst were taken in a 50 mL beaker containing TBAB (50 mg) dissolved in water (10 mL). The contents of the beaker were irradiated under microwave (450 W) for appropriate time as shown in Table 1. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, water was added and solid product obtained. It was filtered off and was purified by recrystallization from ethanol.

Spectral analysis

Essentially pure products were obtained which were confirmed by comparison with authentic samples by their physical constants and characterized by spectral analysis IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectroscopy.

3,3,6,6-tetramethyl-9-(4-chlorophenyl)-2,4,5,7-tetrahydro(2H)-9-hydro(1H)xanthene-1,8-dione

IR (cm⁻¹) : 3100, 2962, 2875, 1678, 1624, 1550, 1361

¹HNMR (δ ppm) : 1.00 (6H, s, C Me₂); 1.12 (6H, s, C Me₂);

2.10 - 2.23 (4H, 2×CH₂); 2.41 (4H, s, 2×CH₂);

4.63 (1H, s, CH); 7.12 (2H, Ar-H); 7.29 (2H, Ar-H)

Mass : 385 (+M)

3,3,6,6-tetramethyl-9-(4-nitrophenyl)-2,4,5,7-tetrahydro(2H)-

9-hydro(1H)-xanthene-1,8-dione

IR (cm⁻¹) : 3070, 2958, 2870, 1654, 1616, 1514, 1361

¹HNMR (δ ppm) : 1.00 (6H, s, C Me₂); 1.12 (6H, s, C Me₂);

2.10 - 2.3 (4H, 2×CH₂); 2.45 (4H, s, 2×CH₂);

4.80 (1H, s, CH); 7.25 (2H, Ar-H); 7.4 (2H, Ar=H)

Mass : 395 (+M)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The condensation of dimedone and aromatic aldehydes with TBAB in presence of the catalyst PNT afforded the corresponding 1,8-dioxooctahydroxanthene derivatives under the microwave conditions.

Several functionalities present in aryl aldehydes such as chloro, nitro, methoxy, methyl and hydroxyl groups tolerated the reaction conditions in 2-3 minutes of short time. Aromatic aldehydes having both electron donating or withdrawing groups reacted readily with dimedone to products in 87-96 % yields (Table 1). As can be seen from the table, it was possible to carry out the reaction within shorter times in moderate to good yields.

Initially the reactions were carried out without addition of TBAB, but with the addition of TBAB as phase transfer agent, the reactions proceeded cleanly. Thus, PNT together with TBAB under microwave irradiation was found to be a suitable method for the condensation of various aromatic aldehydes with dimedone in water to afford the corresponding products.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, a series of 1,8-dioxooctahydroxanthenes were synthesized using PNT as an efficient catalyst by the condensation of aldehydes and dimedone in good yields. All the reactions were conducted in water as a green solvent under microwave irradiation.

Table 1 : Phosphonitrilic chloride catalysed synthesis of various 1,8-dioxooctahydroxanthene derivatives.

Entry	Aldehyde	Time (Min.)	Yield (%)	M.P.(°C) Observed	M.P.(°C) Literature
1		2	96	202-203	205 [81]
2		2.5	94	231-232	228-230 [59]
3		3	87	243-244	241-243 [59]
4		3	89	163-165	164-165 [59]
5		2.5	90	247-250	248-250 [59]
6		3	92	226-228	226 [82]
7		3	91	248-251	246 [81]
8		3	86	187-188	187-189 [81]
9		2.5	96	224-225	221-223 [59]
10		3	92	169-171	168-170 [59]
11		2.5	90	61-63	62-64 [59]
12		2	88	215-217	217-218 [59]
13		3	90	228-230	226-228 [59]

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